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Oxovanadium(IV) Complexes with Imidazole, Benzimidazole and Substituted Benzimidazoles

A. K. SINHA, (Mrs.) URMILA KUMARI, C. P. SINGH
and

L. K. MISHRA*

Department of Chemistry, Patna University,
Patna-800 005

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In previous communications, we reported the complexes of various transition metal ions with benzimidazole and substituted benzimidazoles¹⁻⁷ as well as oxovanadium(IV) complexes with some substituted benzimidazoles⁸. A non-detailed information on oxovanadium(IV) complexes [VO(BzH)₄·(H₂O)]SO₄ and [VO(Bz)₂] is also available⁹. In the present paper we report the preparation and characterisation of VO^{II} complexes with imidazole, benzimidazole and some substituted benzimidazoles.

Experimental

Benzimidazole, 2-methylbenzimidazole and 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole were prepared by reported method¹⁻³. Imidazole and oxovanadium(IV) salts (B.D.H.) were used. 90% ethanol was used for preparation of complexes.

Preparation of complexes: An ethanolic solution of hydrated oxovanadium(IV) salt (0.01 mol in 50 ml 90% ethanol) and a slight excess of ethanolic solution of the appropriate ligands (30–40 ml) were mixed together and refluxed on a steam-bath for 0.5 h when sulphato complexes separated out gradually. The complex chlorides were obtained on concentrating the refluxate to 15–20 ml and cooling it overnight. The complexes, bromide and iodide, were obtained by adding an aqueous solution of potassium bromide/iodide to the resulting solution of the complex chloride and concentrating to half of its volume. The neutral inner complexes were obtained by raising pH of the refluxate to 7–8 by adding an aqueous solution of sodium acetate (2–3 g in 10 ml). The products were filtered, washed with aqueous ethanol and dried over CaCl₂.

The results of elemental analysis, magnetic moment values (at 304 K), reflectance and important ir spectral bands of the complexes are given in Table 1. Magnetic susceptibility, uv and ir spectra were recorded as reported earlier¹⁻³.

Results and Discussion

The analytical results of the complexes and formula are given in Table 1. The sulphato complexes have poor solubility in ethanol, methanol and dioxan whereas the complex halides are fairly soluble in these solvents. The complexes, in general, are soluble in DMF. The DMF solutions of the complex halides and [VO(BzH)₃]SO₄ display electrical conductance value in the range of 105–136 Ω⁻¹ mol⁻¹ cm² indicating the anion to be uncoordinated. The PBzH complexes as well as the sulphato complexes was found to be anhydrous below 120° indicating uncoordinated nature of water molecules. The complex chlorides VO(L)₂Cl₂·nH₂O (L=IzH, BzH or MBzH and n=2 or 3) usually retained one H₂O below 120° indicating that retained H₂O is bonded to VO^{II}. The bischelated complexes [VO(PBzH)₂SO₄].3H₂O, [VO(PBzH)₂]X₂·nH₂O (X=Cl, Br or I and n=2 or 3) and [VO(PBz)₂].3H₂O display magnetic moment value (1.71–1.74 B.M.) equal to spin-only value whereas other complexes display subnormal magnetic moment value (1.59–1.69 B.M.) indicating their dimeric or polymeric character¹⁰.

The electronic reflectance spectra of the complexes exhibited low energy band at 12 800–14 280 cm⁻¹ corresponding to b₂-e_g transition. The second band at 15 300–18 530 cm⁻¹ was assigned to b₂-b₁* transition (10 Dq)¹⁴. The high energy band at 23 500–26 500 cm⁻¹ was assigned to b₂-a₁* transition plus charge transfer absorption. The 10 Dq

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
		M	N	SO ₄ , Cl, Br or I
[VO(IzH) ₂ SO ₄].2H ₂ O	Light pink	12.45 (12.63)	20.68 (20.84)	23.60 (23.82)
[VO(BzH) ₂]SO ₄	Light green	16.10 (9.85)	16.06 (16.24)	18.84 (18.57)
[VO(PBzH) ₂ SO ₄].3H ₂ O	Light green	8.54 (8.39)	13.67 (13.83)	15.58 (15.81)
[VO(MBzH) ₂ SO ₄].3H ₂ O	Light blue	10.74 (10.58)	11.36 (11.64)	20.12 (19.96)
[VO(BzH) ₂ (H ₂ O)]Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O	Dark green	12.08 (11.90)	12.92 (13.09)	16.41 (16.56)
[VO(IzH) ₂ (H ₂ O)]Cl ₂ .H ₂ O	Dark green	16.60 (16.43)	18.21 (18.07)	23.00 (22.87)
[VO(MBzH) ₂ (H ₂ O)]Cl ₂ .H ₂ O	Bluish green	11.49 (11.63)	12.45 (12.79)	16.01 (16.18)
[VO(PBz) ₂].3H ₂ O	Yellowish green	9.90 (10.00)	16.35 (16.50)	—
[VO(PBzH) ₂]Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O	Yellowish green	8.92 (9.03)	14.65 (14.89)	12.43 (12.57)
[VO(PBzH) ₂]Br ₂ .2H ₂ O	Yellowish green	7.65 (7.80)	12.60 (12.87)	24.60 (24.47)
[VO(PBzH) ₂]I ₂ .3H ₂ O	Yellowish green	6.44 (6.66)	10.83 (10.98)	33.43 (33.17)

value for the IzH complexes is maximum, which is quite reasonable¹⁴. Thus the spectral results of the complexes are suggestive of distorted octahedral structure¹⁵.

The ir spectra of the complexes exhibited a broad band at 3400–3320 cm⁻¹ for water molecules¹⁶. The ν_{NH} bands of BzH (3248)⁷, IzH (3280)¹⁴ and MBzH (3218 cm⁻¹)⁷ shifted to lower frequency in their complexes by 40–160 cm⁻¹ and NH bending band to higher frequencies by 10–20 cm⁻¹ suggesting coordination of NH nitrogen to the metal atom. The ν_{C=N} band of ligand also shifted to higher frequencies by 8–15 cm⁻¹ supporting coordination of pyridine nitrogen. The absence of NH proton in VO(PBz)₂.3H₂O supported deprotonation and coordination of NH nitrogen. The ν_{NH} band of PBzH (3249 cm⁻¹) is not affected in its complex halides and sulphato complexes, but ν_{C=N} band shifted to lower frequency indicating coordination of tertiary benzimidazole and pyridine nitrogens¹⁷. The complex sulphates gave characteristic ir bands of ionic sulphate group¹⁷. The splitting of ν₃ and ν₄ bands of sulphate group in [VO(IzH)₂SO₄].2H₂O (1165, 1050; and 623, 608 cm⁻¹), [VO(MBzH)₂SO₄].3H₂O (1145, 1050; and 632, 612 cm⁻¹) and [VO(PBzH)₂SO₄].3H₂O (1115, 1070; and 621, 605 cm⁻¹) indicated the monocoordination of SO₄²⁻ group¹⁷. The ν_{V=O} band was observed as a very strong band at 980–960 cm⁻¹ for [VO(PBzH)₂SO₄].3H₂O and the IzH, BzH as well as MBzH complexes, but shifted to lower frequency in [VO(PBzH)₂]X₂.nH₂O and [VO(PBz)₂].3H₂O suggesting that V=O oxygen is free in the sulphato complexes but V=O–V=O chain is present in the complex halides.⁸ The aquo-complexes exhibited a broad medium band at 650–630 cm⁻¹ attributed to ρ_w (H₂O) of coordinated water. Due to a number of ir bands of the ligand molecules in far-ir region, M–L band could not be assigned definitely.

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